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Proceedings

Editor: Ivan Spasojević

Technical support: Jelena Korać Jačić

Cover design: Zoran Beloševac

Publisher: Faculty of Chemistry, Serbian Biochemical Society

Printed by: Colorgrafx, Belgrade

Serbian Biochemical Society

Eleventh Conference

Scientific meeting of an international character

September 22nd and 23rd, 2022, Novi Sad, Serbia

“Amazing Biochemistry”

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

577.1(048)

SERBIAN Biochemical Society. Scientific meeting of an international character (11 ; 2022 ; Novi Sad)

"Amazing Biochemistry" : [proceedings] / Serbian Biochemical Society, Eleventh Conference, Scientific meeting of an international character, September 22nd and 23rd, 2022, Novi Sad, Serbia ; [editor Ivan Spasojević]. - Belgrade : Faculty of Chemistry : Serbian Biochemical Society, 2022 (Belgrade : Colorgrafx). - 165 str. ; 23 cm

Tiraž 150. - Str. 19: Foreword / Ivan Spasojević. - Bibliografija uz većinu radova.

ISBN 978-86-7220-124-6 (FOC)

а) Биохемија -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 73285385

The impact of albumin/globulin ratio on COVID-19 mortality

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Albumin is the most abundant protein in blood and low concentration is associated with decreased production or increased loss. Globulins are more diverse group of proteins, and some of them such as immunoglobulins are specifically involved in acute and chronic infections. Albumin/globulin ratio (AGR) is a biomarker with potentially prognostic value in COVID-19 patients with sepsis¹. The aim of research is to compare AGR value at survivors vs non-survivors, and note if there are differences among women and men. The study retrospectively enrolled 88 confirmed COVID-19 patients with sepsis (aged 22-84 years; 59 men, 29 women), who were hospitalized in a tertiary care hospital from November 2020 to January 2022. Demographic data and laboratory values were collected from medical records (the following variables for each patient: age, sex, serum albumin level, globulin level, total serum proteins, albumin/globulin ratio and 28-day mortality). Patients were divided into 2 groups according to outcome: survivors (33 patients) and non-survivors (55 patients). Normality test (Shapiro-Wilk), descriptive statistic and statistical analysis were performed by software IBM SPSS[®] Statistics 23.0. Differences among groups and subgroups (sexes) were estimated using the independent T-test. P-value <0,05 had been considered significant. Mean AGR was not much higher in survival ($\bar{x}=1,23$) than in non-survival group ($\bar{x}=1,14$) and there are no significant difference among sexes. But graphical presentation of data (scatter plot and box plots) showed better correlation between low albumin and death at men. Thus, a larger study with more patients is needed for more exact correlation.

References

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